

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part-XXXVIII : Synthesis and *in vitro* Screening of 4,6-Dimethyl-5-(Arylazo/ N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrimidin-2-thiols

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Manuscript received 23 February 1982, accepted 10 March 1983

4,6-Dimethylpyrimidin-2-thiol was synthesised by condensing thiourea with pentane-2,4-dione. This was later coupled with different diazotised simple and sulphonamide bases when the corresponding 4,6-dimethyl-5-(arylazo/N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrimidin-2-thiols were obtained. The structures were confirmed by elemental analysis and ir and nmr spectral data. When tested *in vitro*, the thiol compounds showed considerable activity against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. pyocyanea*.

PYRIMIDINE ring systems having a mercapto group have been known to be tumor inhibitors¹, antimycotic², antileukemic³, tuberculostat⁴, anti-thyroid⁵ and hypoglycaemic⁶ agents. Further, the 5-aryazo analogues of 2-thiopyrimidines have been reported to possess anticancer properties⁷. Keeping this in view and encouraged by our findings with pyrimidinediones^{8,9} and pyrimidin-2-ols¹⁰, 4,6-dimethylpyrimidine-2-thiol has been synthesised and later coupled with different diazotised simple and sulphonamide bases to obtain the corresponding 4,6-dimethyl-5-(arylazo/N-substituted *p*-sulphamylbenzeneazo)pyrimidin-2-thiols of the type Ia, b.

Ia : R = C₆H₄R₁ ; Ib : R = C₆H₄SO₂NHR₁

All the synthesised products were subjected to *in vitro* screening by cup-plate agar diffusion method

against *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. pyocyanea* at two different concentrations of 50 µg/ml and 100 µg/ml. The results with 50 µg/ml have been entered in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—4,6-DIMETHYL-5-(ARYLAZO)PYRIMIDIN-2-THIOLS
(Ia : R = C₆H₄R₁)

Sl. No.	R ₁	m.p. °C	Yield %	Antibacterial activity		
				<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. pyocyanea</i>
1.	H	165	40	++	+	-
2.	<i>o</i> -Me	153	33	-	+	+
3.	<i>m</i> -Me	105	31	+	+	+
4.	<i>p</i> -Me	106	33	++	+	++
5.	<i>o</i> -Cl	91	38	++	-	+
6.	<i>m</i> -Cl	90	36	+	-	-
7.	<i>p</i> -Cl	148	44	++	+	++
8.	<i>p</i> -Br	117	39	++	+	++
9.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	106	44	+++	++	++
10.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	109	46	++	+	+
11.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	118	36	+++	+	++
12.	2,5-Cl ₂	148	46	++++	+	++

The compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

TABLE 2 - 4,6-DIMETHYL-5-(N-SUBSTITUTED *p*-SULPHAMYL-BENZENEAZO)PYRIMIDIN-2-THIOLS

(Ib : R = C₆H₄SO₂NHR₁)

Sl. No.	R ₁	m.p. °C	Yield %	Antibacterial activity		
				<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. pyocyanea</i>
1.	H	260	40	+	-	-
2.	Acetyl	252	39	-	+	+
3.	<i>o</i> -Me, Ph	226	35	+	+	+
4.	<i>p</i> -Me, Ph	142	38	+	+	-
5.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ , Ph	192	43	+	+	-
6.	<i>o</i> -MeO, Ph	> 300	40	+	+	+
7.	Pyrimidin-2-yl	235	40	+	+	+
8.	4,6-Me ₂ pyrimidin-2-yl	209	40	+	+	+
9.	2,6-Me ₂ pyrimidin-4-yl	> 300	38	+	+	-
10.	4-Me.pyrimidin-2-yl	143	32	-	-	-
11.	2,6-(MeO) ₂ pyrimidin-4-yl	> 300	35	++	++	++

The compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

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Experimental

Synthesis of 4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-thiol: Thiourea (38.0 g; 0.5 mol) and pentane-2,4-dione (50.0 g; 0.5 mol) were taken in ethanol (250 ml) and refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. Conc. hydrochloric acid (67 ml) was then added dropwise and refluxing continued for further 1 hr. On keeping the contents overnight, 4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-thiol hydrochloride separated out in light yellow shining crystals. It was filtered, dissolved in water and neutralized carefully with aqueous sodium hydroxide (10%) to furnish light yellow small crystals of 4,6-dimethylpyrimidine-2-thiol, m.p. 218°, yield, 42 g (60%). (Found: C, 51.2; H, 5.6. $C_8H_{10}N_2S$ requires C, 51.4; H, 5.7%). IR ν_{max}^{KBr} cm^{-1} : 1550 (C=C), 1613 (C=N), 2597 (SH), 2941 (C-H). NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.25 (s, 6H); 6.58 (s, ring H), 5.0 (hump, 1H, SH).

Synthesis of 4,6-dimethyl-5-(aryloxy)N-substituted p-sulphamylbenzeneazo pyrimidin-2-thiol: To a solution of 4,6-dimethylpyrimidin-2-thiol (0.0025 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) containing sodium acetate (10 g) was added a well cooled solution of diazotised simple or sulphonamide base (0.0025 mol). The solid obtained by addition of ice-cold water and stirring was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol or glacial acetic acid or a mixture of DMF with either of the two. IR ν_{max}^{KBr} cm^{-1} : 1560-1580 (C=N), 1510-1540 (C=C), 3106-3115 (C-H), 2604-2620 (SH), 1535-1567 (N=N), ~1300 and ~1090 (SO₂ asymmetric and symmetric stretching).

The absence of any signal at 6.58 δ (ring proton) in the nmr spectra of the coupled products indicates that coupling has taken place.

Antibacterial activity:

The results of screening at 50 $\mu g/ml$ indicate that 4,6-dimethyl-5-(aryloxy)pyrimidin-2-thiols are quite active against all the three micro-organism and the activity is in the order *S. aureus* > *P. pyocyanea* > *E. coli*. The activity increases as the electronegativity of the group on the phenyl ring attached through an azo linkage increases. Replacement of aryloxy by sulphonamidobenzeneazo group renders these less active against the three organisms.

In general, pyrimidin-2-thiols were found to be more active than corresponding pyrimidin-2-ols studied earlier¹⁰.

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